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WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER: BASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF MENTAL HEALTH WORKBOOK TOWARDS WELL-BEING OF
MOTHERS OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS**

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Lived Experiences of Selected Mothers Nurturing Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Basis in the Development of Mental Health Workbook towards Well-Being of Mothers of Children with Special Needs

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to provide insight into the experiences of Filipino mothers in Cavite, specifically in behavioral centers of Chrysalides Therapy Center in Bacoor and The Bright Future Behavioral Center in Imus, who take care of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Researchers looked at the personal narratives of ten Filipino mothers from two behavioral centers in Cavite using qualitative phenomenological analysis. To get useful information about their experiences, a fourteen-question semi-structured format was used. The questions were made using the SWOT framework to help them figure out their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats when it comes to providing care and support for children with ASD and how it affects their daily lives. The data was analyzed through thematic analysis to find themes and patterns. It was found that mothers have strengths like having support from family and society, knowing and caring for their child, and sometimes being religious. However, they are also vulnerable because they deal with a lot of stress and negative emotions, have trouble setting priorities, and have limited access to many health services. There are also times when the family gives relief and helps people bond, yet there are also threats, like disruptive behavior from children, social judgment, and financial challenges. Based on the themes that were found, it is suggested that a workbook be developed with tasks like crossword puzzles, origami, and photo journaling that will keep people interested and help them reach their goals. Its goal is to help mothers live better lives and improve their mental and physical wellness. Overall, this study helps people learn more about the lives of Filipino mothers and offers services that can make their daily experiences and the lives of their children better.

Keywords: *ASD Mothers, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Neurodivergent Children, lived experiences of mothers, Mental Health of ASD Mothers*

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a lifelong, complex neurological disorder characterized by impairments in social interaction, communication, and behavioral flexibility (Baird-Bate, 2019). The experiences of individuals with ASD are diverse and often comorbid, reflecting the complex nature of the disorder. Studies indicate that parenting stress experienced by mothers of children with ASD in Southeast Asian nations is affected by various aspects, including social support, the severity of autism symptoms, socioeconomic challenges, and parental perspectives about autism. Moreover, caregivers' load has been linked to certain issue behaviors displayed by children with ASD, including irritability, social withdrawal, and hyperactivity (Chua et al., 2023). According to the Department of Health (DOH), as cited by Torregozza (2023), the number of people in the Philippines who have ASD has been steadily rising over the past ten years. In 2008, the number was five hundred thousand. In 2018, it was one million. This rise makes it clear that the government needs to help people with autism spectrum and their families right away, especially those who are struggling financially and are unable to pay for the therapies they need, like speech therapy, occupational therapy, applied behavioral analysis, and verbal behavior therapy.

Highlighting the prevalence of ASD, Papadopoulos's (2021) study focuses on the issues faced by mothers, particularly in countries with insufficient support facilities. Factors that contribute to the stress experienced by families caring for children with special needs include the intensity of their symptoms as well as financial obligations. The research also highlights the significance of societal assistance in reducing stress for mothers. One must get under the surface of difficulties and examine the complicated structure of emotions that these mothers have to experience every day in order to fully grasp the conditions of their everyday lives. Empathetic and effective mental health programs can be guided by the emotional journeys of these women, which include both the deep affection that propels them through difficulties and the times of hopelessness that may result in them feeling marginalized. Due to the significant influence of ASD on families globally, it is crucial to investigate the actual experiences of mothers who care for children with ASD, especially in places that are not prominently documented in the mainstream. Gaining insight into the distinct factors that cause stress and the strategies these mothers use to deal with these issues can help in creating specific therapies that aim to enhance their mental health and overall well-being.

Research Questions

In order to fully comprehend and address each aspect of this problem, the research questions are tailored to the SWOT analysis method. This will involve assessing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats faced by these mothers in raising their children with autism spectrum disorder. Specifically, the inquiries are:

1. What strengths do mothers of children with ASD have that keep them from falling apart and giving up on caring for their children? How do they find their children very rewarding to care for?
2. What are some relational or psychological aspects that count as weaknesses of mothers of children with ASD?
3. What and how do mothers gain opportunities such as existing support programs and moments of respite?
4. What specific threats do the mothers face and figure to be the cause of their interrupted peace of mind and well-being?
5. What other emergent themes could be formulated?

Literature Review

Extending or being specific about the manifestation of ASD, the signs usually get recognized full-blown when the child reaches two years of age, but five to six months in the developmental time can also have indicators (Chee, n.d., as cited in Kadir, 2020) such as slow motor development or less movement - wherein a several-month old infant cannot recognize when they are called, do not exhibit happiness, or cannot mimic facial expressions, other than that, when the child is wanting extra attention and is not cautious consistently through age, and communication deficits such as not exhibiting baby talk, unresponsiveness when called by name, absence of eye contact, or even not smiling (Kadir, 2020). It was further inspected in Nepomuceno's (2022) study that the family caregivers had to ask for professional assistance due to a number of factors, including unusual behavior, mannerisms, and third parties, that eventually resulted in the diagnosis. The family caregivers stated that the majority of the most typical unusual actions included flapping of the hands, tiptoeing, sensitivity to loud noises, covering the ears, getting quickly distracted, staying silent when called in, and avoiding eye contact. But prior to that, several of the family caregivers had already encountered challenges before they discovered their loved one's diagnosis, and it was challenging for them to understand ASD at first. Mansur et al. (2022) also highlight that the diagnosis of ASD in their child insinuates grief among parents, causing them to undergo the five stages of the grief model, which is denial or rejection as termed in the study, anger, bargaining, depression, before moving to acceptance.

Leosala's 2023 study aims at how cultural ideas, beliefs, and behaviors affect how parents think about and respond to their child's condition and behavior. The cultural setting can affect how mothers of children with ASD ask for help, how they feel about their child's disability, and how easily they ask for support from others. This makes it easier for people to understand the different experiences of mothers from different cultures. It is imperative for moms to take care of themselves and get help from their communities to stay healthy. Mothers can get their strength and resilience back by joining support groups, getting professional help, and learning good ways to deal with stress. By understanding what women and their children go through, they can make their community more accepting and kinder, which will help them stay strong and committed to their children.

Given the recent COVID-19 pandemic, meeting the educational needs of neurodivergent children has become a challenge to the parents as they embrace the role of being teachers. The parents expressed difficulty in facilitating their child's learning as they have to check the modular material on their own first before delivery to their child, who has easily waning motivation and even, in some cases, difficulty in writing. Nevertheless, the parents persisted and coped with the problem-focused style by listening to teacher or professional advice, seizing the perfect mood or time for learning, working through and embracing the child's individuality, and keeping the faith against all odds - religiosity. These were the themes figured in Bangoy's (2023) study. The translation into the new normal was not easy either. Borro and Ceballo (2023) presented similar themes regarding the challenges of raising neurodivergent children post-pandemic in the Philippines.

In Abdullah et al. (2022), labeling as closely tied to stigmatization is highly anticipated by mothers, one in particular, when her child reacts violently and punches other kids due to sensitivity to noise, she expects no opportunity for justification as the condition of her child may not suffice to others as an excuse for bad behavior. Other than aggression, though, repetitive behaviors and even self-hurt are a cause of concern in Tathgur and Kang (2021).

Studies by Brohan et al. (2010) and Mak and Kwok (2010), which were cited by Serchuk et al. (2021), show that self-care and fear of being judged by others are both important factors. The study talked about how mothers' anger and sadness responses to self-help behaviors are related to how they deal with shame, depression, hiding, and their quality of life. The data show that stigmatization from the outside and inside interact in a complex way. This helps people understand the mental burden that mothers of children with ASD have. Mothers who feel like they have to hide their problems may be lonelier and have a lower quality of life. This shows that mothers' health can be hurt by keeping things from other people. These facts show how important it is to set up support groups and areas where moms can share their issues and ask for help. A lot of mothers deal with problems in different ways, as shown by Leosala (2023). Dealing with stress can look different for each person. Some people lean on friends and family for support, while others do things for themselves, like meditate or work out. This leads to the next large body of literature: each mother deals with the difficulties of caring for her children by using methods that work for her and drawing on her own strengths and resources.

Indirectly, negative emotions can be felt by the mothers if stigmatization is delivered through the peers of the sibling of the child with ASD. In Abdullah et al. (2022), the sibling of one interviewee's mother gets to participate and expresses how the condition itself strains the sibling's relationship with the ASD child, especially when venturing together in public, such as in a school setting. Not only does having an ASD child affect the mother's relationship with her other child, but the pressing demands of having a child with ASD also leads to strain in spousal relationships (Tathgur & Kang, 2021). Another thing that causes worry to mothers is when their child is about to enter adolescence, and more so if their child is a girl.

In comparison to Middle Eastern countries, according to a study by Alshaigi et al. (2019), Thirty-seven participant parents whose children were diagnosed with ASD in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, said they experienced stigma. Mothers are more likely than fathers to feel and act stigmatized. The effect of autism on children in Saudi society, along with cultural issues connected with their people and social growth, presents several hurdles and problems for parents parenting children with ASD. Although the majority of parents did not feel stigmatized for raising an ASD child, the minority of parents scored high on questions about feeling stigma. Furthermore, caregivers of male and female ASD children were not significantly different from each other statistically.

However, mothers of ASD children had significantly higher levels of self-perception and actual stigmatization than fathers did. This result was in accordance with the research done by Towairqi et al. (2015; as cited in Alshaigi et al., 2019). In the Saudi context still, a study by Sulaimani & Mursi (2022) on how mothers deal with stigma, mothers were the first recipients of parenting blame, and the results do not differ as much from other studies, and most themes presented overlap with Alshaigi et al. (2019).

Arguably, there is a bit of indifference for cases of single parenting as their caregiving experiences were also given recognition. In one study in the Filipino context, notably, their lived experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic were brought into the limelight, and what sets them apart from typical nuclear families is the prevalence of economic struggle and social isolation, which they experience in a more severe manner. Not only do they have to deal with or juggle multiple responsibilities, deal with discrimination, and give up social engagements to favor parenthood, but they also need to safeguard their parenting role - that is to assume the responsibility of a parent and instill discipline (Berdan & Distor, 2024).

An Australian researcher named Baird-Bate (2019) did a qualitative visual narrative study at the Queensland University of Technology that shows the struggles and strengths of mothers who have children with ASD. The study looked at the daily lives of some mothers whose children have ASD. After that, the pictures and stories were analyzed by theme using a method called "photo journaling," which Baird-Bate used to help care for her own autistic son. The study showed that even though there are risks in caring for a child with ASD, mothers are still resilient. It also gave different caregivers different ideas about what resilience and coping mean in taking care of children with ASD—accepting and adjusting to the different kinds of normalcy that come with their children, which they see as a gift.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized a qualitative phenomenological approach to analyze human experiences by studying the descriptions given by those who are personally involved. Researchers refer to these encounters as lived experiences, as they can be accustomed to exploring the subjects without bringing any changes or influence on the main variables of the study. This would be ideal for the study of the lived experiences of selected mothers of children with ASD.

Participants

The participants of the study are ten (10) selected mothers of children with ASD who have their children enrolled at two behavioral centers in the City of Cavite, Region IV-A, one from Bacoor and another from Imus.

Instrument

For the purpose of intellectual inquiry, a peer-reviewed interview questionnaire consisting of a total of fourteen (12) questions narrowed from the initial twenty-two (22) items designed to gather relevant information about the respondents' lived experiences was made. It was patterned to the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis framework.

Procedure

Responses from participants were transcribed from the recorded interviews of each participant. The interview notes were gathered if the individual had refused to have the tape-recorded. To find the main themes and categories, the transcriptions were read and examined. Important ideas and sentences in the transcriptions were given codes using open coding. Subcategories were developed, and codes were correlated using axial coding to relate themes. As they progressed, the researchers created main themes by selectively classifying subcategories into more general categories. Then, the results are presented in an analytical report together with instances of participant comments that back up every theme. The researchers prioritized consideration, and it was made up of ethical issues like participant privacy and sensitivities.

Results and Discussion

Following the framework of SWOT analysis, this chapter discusses the different responses of the participants and how it aligns with the collected set of related literature, and how it answers the established questions of the research.

The table below presents the analysis of the data arranged in specific themes namely (1) Strength of Mothers (2) Weakness of Mothers (3) Opportunities for Mothers (4) Threats for Mothers.

These main themes will have subordinate themes that will cover more of the experiences of mothers having a child with ASD.

Table 1. *SWOT Analysis of Lived Experiences of Selected Mothers Nurturing Children with ASD*

Themes	Subthemes
Strengths	Support System Collective Support Intellectual Progress of the Child Expressing Affection Acknowledgement of Diagnosis Overcoming Health Challenges of both Parent and Child
Weaknesses	Self-doubt and Self-depreciation Worries/Doubts about the Delayed Milestone/s of the Child Limited Communication
Opportunities	Social Benefits Exposure to Social/ Educational Setting Bonding with the Child Personal Solace
Threats	Sudden Outburst Food Aversion Shelving Personal Life and Fulfillment

Strengths

Support System

A common answer of all of the respondents when it comes to identifying whom they draw their strength from through the interviews is a support system further classified into immediate family, extended family, and friends. Respondents repeatedly stress the value of their immediate family parents and spouses as sources of understanding and support. It extends to the literature as a recognized support structure for mothers caring for children with ASD, the bracket including immediate and extended family, schools, professionals, and online communities as per Ilias et al., (2018). Lei and Kantor (2021) also back this up in their study of Chinese families' social support systems, and Baranda and Ebrahim (2019) follow through with parental investment and parenting style. All respondents recognize the value their family provides as contributing to their strength.

Collective Support

Another aspect of the strength of the mother is the collective support subtheme that they get from those around them. Collective support includes how other people help the mother by sharing her responsibilities, such as helping the mother take care of the child, do house chores, and provide financial support. Four out of ten respondents say that financial backing contributes to ease of the situation, congruent with Ilias et al.'s 2018 findings about financial difficulty being a predictor of parental stress. With the study's findings, the reverse of it is a strength. The recognition and utility of collective support is also backed up by findings from multiple literature, including Abdullah et al. (2022), Leosala (2023), and Borro and Ceballo (2023).

Intellectual Progress of the Child

Another contributory to maternal strength is knowing their children themselves; part of it is learning the intellectual capacities of their children and their natural charms and innocence, albeit their neurodivergence and what makes them distinct as their own. Baird-Bate (2019) also touches on this as indicated in her paper that she was raising an ASD child of her own and that the experience is very dynamic and not always distressing. There is space for holistic growth (Nepomuceno, 2022) and the positive experiences of caregiving (Younesi et al., 2024).

In addition to being a milestone stage in language learning, this developmental milestone is also a critical time when children begin to communicate their needs, wants, and feelings more effectively. In highlighting this change, Respondent #2 points out that her child's ability to communicate directly helped her better grasp his wants and preferences. As it signifies a major turning point in their child's development and opens up a closer relationship, mothers may find this change to be immensely satisfying although non-conforming to developmental norms, as suggested by Abdullah et al. (2022).

Comparably, another Respondent #5 enjoys her child's few but significant linguistic expressions, particularly when they are accompanied by laughter. It is clear from the simplicity of her child's "2 to 3 words, 5 words" that even little vocal communication can strengthen the link between a parent and child. The baby's growing capacity to engage more successfully with their surroundings and their mothers characterizes this developmental stage, which can be a thrill and a comfort for mothers seeing these first words and phrases.

Expressing Affection

Another recurring theme is the expression of affection, which mothers find endearing. Across those who responded, the affectionate expressions are different but always significant. Respondent #4 talks of how kind her child is, especially when he tries to make amends

by giving kisses and embraces after recognizing he made a mistake. This action demonstrates the child's emotional intelligence as well as their want to keep their mother in a loving connection. This is a big leap for some mothers who have inexpressive children, which is a hallmark for diagnosis (Chee, n.d. as cited in Kadir, 2020). Respondents #8 and #9 underline even more how devoted their children are. The phrase "super lambing" (very loving) mentioned by Respondent #8 suggests regular expressions of love. One quality that Respondent #9 credits to their parenting is that her children often express love verbally. Furthermore, Respondent #10 emphasizes the value of family togetherness for her child, who says he is happy to see the family together. Another kind of affection, this inclination for family connection shows how much the child values the emotional stability that comes from family ties. Mothers may find great satisfaction in these times spent together since they show how caring and supportive family surroundings are.

Acknowledgement of Diagnosis

Moving on to overcoming denial as constituting maternal strength, when it comes to accepting their child's condition, seven out of ten participants pertaining to the transition itself is a source of strength, and it is most likely preceded by being hopeful for their children and that their condition is not always severely distressing. Nepomuceno (2022) calls it "broadening their sense of understanding" as a subtheme. Acceptance is highly noted in Leosala (2023) as the mediator to persistence to provide for the child. According to Mansur et al. (2022), acceptance is the endpoint once the mothers or parents navigate the grief of diagnosis.

Relating to the child is another recognized contributor to maternal strength still understanding and accommodating ASD, which is the way the mother empathizes with her child. One respondent described that their child mirrored how she was when she was young and that both she and her husband are tolerant of diversity so naturally, the condition of their child is met without resistance.

Overcoming Health Challenges for Both Parent and Child

Overcoming health challenges for the parent and the child is one of the more important themes that came out of the research. The parents' emotional and psychological well-being is severely impacted by these events. The personal experiences that the respondents shared demonstrate the great challenges and anxieties they encounter, as well as the close emotional bonds that these misfortunes create. Also, since among the factors, ASD diagnosis can be physiological in origin, these findings are in cohesion with the cases or tragic incidents in Tathgur and Kang's (2021) similar study. The first participant describes the immediate health concern following the birth of her baby Theo with sepsis, and she describes the unexpected result of his autism diagnosis. This story emphasizes how unpredictably health issues arise and how difficult they are for mothers. This event emphasizes the two layers of health emergencies: the immediate physical health issue and the long-term developmental effects.

Respondent #4 considers the hernia surgery on her child one of the hardest things she has ever had to go through. Her genetic defect, APAS (Antiphospholipid Antibody Syndrome), which resulted in three miscarriages, made her situation worse. A mother must overcome significant mental and physical obstacles when she witnesses her kid undergo surgery and when she experiences the loss and trauma of multiple miscarriages. This emphasizes the interdependence of the health of parents and children, where the health of one greatly affects the other. Respondent #5 relates their terrifying experience of giving delivery on a plane at 27 weeks along. From the perils of a premature birth to the difficulties of giving birth in an unusual and maybe dangerous setting, there are many levels of risk and anxiety in this scenario. Premature birth itself presents a number of health issues that need extensive medical attention and ongoing observation. This narrative perfectly captures the terrible situations that some parents have to deal with and the amazing effort they make to guarantee their child's life and well-being.

Weaknesses

Self-doubt and Self-depreciation

Mothers often and universally face self-doubt, as the answers made clear. Every mother tells a different story that, taken together creates a picture of the inner battles they endure. Given this, the related themes identified by Bangoy (2023), Borro and Ceballo (2023), Berdan and Distor (2024) about the parents doubting themselves were not exclusive to and predate the COVID-19 health crisis. Though she recognizes the assistance she has, Respondent #1 still battles self-doubt, implying that internal emotions of inadequacy can endure in the absence of outside assistance. In pondering how a child's behavior might directly cause parental self-doubt, Respondent #4 questions her behaviors and ability when she cannot grasp her child's demands. After her child was diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder, Respondent #5 spoke of how she became incredibly self-conscious and questioned her capacity to oversee and give her child the attention they needed. As an example of the ongoing, draining nature of self-doubt in parenting, Respondent #6 asks herself if she is giving enough and parenting well. Fearing the long-term effects of her decision to limit her child's exposure to the outside world and reliance on technology, respondent #9 questions her parenting techniques. These encounters, taken together, demonstrate the complex nature of motherhood-related self-doubt, which is impacted by both internal fears and outside obstacles pertaining to the behavior, medical conditions, and developmental requirements of their children.

Worries/ Doubts about the Delayed Milestone/s of the Child

The stories that the responders told brought to light a number of important facets of the difficulties associated with children's delayed milestones. First off, the constant worry parents have about speech and motor ability delays emphasizes how important these developmental milestones are to them to ease inclusion in school (Cheng & Lai, 2023). Sometimes the earliest signs of possible

developmental problems, delays in these areas, call for quick attention and action. Parents suffer a great deal emotionally, to start with. The responses indicate a heavy emotional load by describing emotions of uncertainty, disbelief, and dissatisfaction, which are the natural tensions described in Leosala (2023). This is especially clear from Respondent #4's story, in which unhappiness and continuous anxiety result from therapy not producing any improvement, a sign of enduring and endless commitment (Abdullah et al., 2022). According to Respondents #5 and #10, these feelings are made worse by comparisons with other kids, which can intensify feelings of inadequacy and worry about the future of their child, as similarly discussed by Tathgur and Kang (2021).

Third, the respondents' encounters emphasize the value of early identification and action. Parents have shown initiative in addressing developmental issues by identifying red signals (expounded in Kadir, 2020), such as the inability to respond to a name (Respondent #6) and choosing to seek therapy (Respondent #4). Still, the conflicting opinions on how well these interventions worked point to the necessity of more thorough and encouraging materials for parents dealing with these difficulties.

Limited Communication

One recurring issue that emphasizes the challenges parents have when their children have trouble expressing themselves verbally is limited communication. Communication difficulties cause the child and the parents to feel frustrated, confused, and under emotional stress.

Effectively attending to the needs and feelings of the child becomes difficult when they are unable to express themselves vocally when upset. It can be constricting and frequently insufficient to explain complicated demands and feelings when one relies only on nonverbal communication, such as physical touch.

Opportunities

Social Benefits

One respondent points out the concrete advantage of getting her child a PWD (Persons with Disabilities) ID. Her child benefits financially from the 20% discount on medications and therapy that the PWD ID offers. The narratives of the responders show how social advantages, especially the PWD ID, which provides savings on necessities like medications and therapies, have somewhat relieved them. The reduction of financial strain on families with special needs children is made possible in large part by these perks. Still, the answers also point to important holes in all-encompassing support.

First, although the PWD ID offers substantial savings, Respondents #1 and #3 say that these advantages are restricted and do not meet more extensive financial needs. The emphasis on savings as opposed to cash aid implies that, although beneficial, these actions are insufficient to completely solve the financial difficulties these families are facing. Second, the MSWD experience of Respondent #4 demonstrates that some parents are eligible for financial support for the expense of therapy. This shows that depending on the support systems of local governments, social benefits are not always available or easily accessible. The ambiguity over whether the help is financial or medical emphasizes the inconsistent and unclear nature of the help offered. Finally, the knowledge that Respondent #5 has extra help available through autistic groups implies that social advantages go beyond what the government offers and include networks of support in the community. Parents looking for financial help for therapy and other expenses may find great value in these organizations, which highlights the value of peer and community support in understanding available benefits.

Exposure to Social/Educational Setting

One mother (Respondent #2) said that her son Theo excelled in a special education (SPED) school as well as a therapy center. Theo not only spoke clearly in these encouraging environments, but his helpful demeanor and leadership abilities also won him over as a teacher favorite. This demonstrates how children can be nurtured and included in an environment that allows them to show off their skills and even assume leadership positions. One other mother (Respondent #3) compared her child's experiences in a behavioral center with those in a regular school. Although her child was hesitant and frequently opposed to attending the regular school, he behaved very differently at the behavioral center. He entered there voluntarily and did not throw tantrums, which suggests a greater degree of comfort and adjustment in the specialist environment. This implies that settings designed with the particular requirements of children with special needs can greatly lower anxiety and behavioral problems and promote a more seamless transition. This example of sudden transition was counter to Cheng and Lai's (2023) conclusion that children with ASD experience difficulty in school.

These encounters, taken together, highlight how important it is for children with special needs to have appropriate and supportive learning environments in order to promote good adjustment and active involvement. Better communication, sociability, and general development seem to be facilitated by the positive reinforcement, specialized help, and inclusive possibilities offered by therapy centers and SPED schools. These stories emphasize how crucial it is for the development, welfare, and long-term success of children with special needs that educational settings be prepared to accommodate their particular demands.

Bonding with the Child

The bonding topic highlights the many approaches that mothers use to develop close bonds with their special needs children. Through frequent travels, imaginative activities, persistent efforts, and these mothers show how committed they are to raising deep relationships with their children. Mothers who give bonding activities top priority support their children's social and emotional growth as well as

their sense of love, security, and belonging in the family.

Personal Solace

The participants talked on how they take care of themselves and deal with parenting special needs children. Baird-Bate (2019), describes these as moments of respite. These pursuits stand in for their attempts to maintain their health and get some relaxation while providing care. Mother Respondent #4 claimed her primary form of self-care was ministry. House calls were a calming and fulfilling release from motherhood for her. This underlines the need for recharging with worthwhile activities away from caregiving. Reading books and seeing movies are two more motherly self-care activities that are important (Respondent #10). Her activities allow her to decompress after a demanding day and escape the pressures of motherhood.

The need to maintain mental and emotional health is emphasized by the focus on regularity in self-care practices. Whether they schedule daily or occasional self-care, mothers are better equipped to handle parenting challenges and provide their children with the finest care possible.

Threats

Emotional Outburst

The child's problem behaviors include tantrums, and as the primary caregiver, the participant mothers are usually the first recipients of such instances (Sulaimani & Mursi, 2022). The literature by Chua et al. (2023) lightly touches on this as problem behaviors, other than tantrums, which are thought to be manipulated by some parents in the Masanka tribe in Catubigan (2023). Because of hyperactivity also and some instances of stimming, such behaviors are considered maternal threats as some mothers think of it as an avenue for embarrassment but given the thin line between what is typical and atypical for a child - neurodivergent or neurotypical, the responses appear to not clearly distinguish between what is neurodivergent and neurotypical mechanisms.

Food Aversion

Mothers highlighted the difficulties they have in providing their ASD children with enough nourishment and voiced worries about their picky eating habits and food aversion. The responses show how children with special needs' nutritional intake and general well-being are impacted by food aversion and picky eating habits. Mothers find it difficult to provide their children with the right nutrition and to guarantee their growth and development when they follow these eating habits. Mothers raising ASD children may find their caregiving experience even more difficult when food aversion and picky eating habits compound pre-existing problems with sensory sensitivity or developmental problems.

Shelving Personal Life and Fulfillment

Another source of threat is the needed adjustments and compromises to properly care for their child. Several, if not few, of the respondents mentioned giving up something about their work, or even part-time like owning a store or being a real estate agent, because of the need to actually dedicate their time to be a full-time mom, which is a distinguished theme in Berdan and Distor (2024)'s phenomenological study on single parents of children with ASD. Findings suggest that shelving personal life and fulfillment is not limited to single parents.

Other Emergent Themes

The researchers have incorporated and compiled other emergent themes for those themes that do not qualify to be included in the SWOT analysis themes.

Table 2. *Other Emergent Themes from Lived Experiences of Mothers Nurturing Children with ASD*

<i>Other Emergent Themes</i>
Dead Malice
Coping of Mothers

Dead Malice

Clearly indifferent, Respondent #1 said they do not give an ounce of importance to what other people think. Respondent #4 shared this opinion, stressing that understanding and encouraging their child comes first before trying to defend or explain actions to complete strangers. Respondent #5 offered an effective approach in which they occasionally use their child's identity booklet to avoid any misunderstandings in advance. Similar in their disregard for public opinion, respondent #6 concentrated on their child. The attitude was summed up nicely by respondent #9, who said they have no concern or care when people gaze at them. Similar to the thought by Abdullah et al. (2022), when mothers do not actively find opportunity for justification.

Coping of Mothers

The mothers' responses show a range of coping strategies they use to deal with the difficulties in raising special needs children.

Depending on the children and support networks to practice their own beliefs and take care of themselves are among these tactics. Religiosity is covered as a theme in plenty of sources, including but not limited to Abdullah et al. (2022), Nepomuceno (2022), and Berdan & Distor (2024). Further, problem-focused and emotion-focused coping (Chin et al., 2023) were identified to coincide with the results, but self-care and avoidant coping strategies were also identified.

Respondent #1 said that the main source of coping is the children. Respondent #2 takes solace in personal hygiene and shopping. Coping for Respondents #3 and #6 depends on having a strong support network. The need for their solid faith and relationship with God was underlined by Respondents #4 and #5. While Respondent #10 depends on thinking of their child and the duty they carry to keep them motivated and focused, Respondent #8 emphasizes the need to treat oneself and make sure they have leisure time.

The answers show that mothers combine emotional, social, and spiritual coping mechanisms in an extensive way. One recurring topic is their children's emotional support and their intense sense of duty to them. Friends and family are among the social support networks that are essential for offering both emotional and practical help. Some mothers find great solace and strength in their spirituality and faith in God. Shopping and making time for personal leisure can help mothers to decompress and control their stress.

Conclusions

The strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that Filipino mothers who care for children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) face were explored in this study. Mothers that show resilience are those who accept their child's circumstances, depend on family, and to be resilient in spite of their challenges. They nevertheless also deal with increased stress, negative emotions, and limitations on social benefits. By teaching their child to be self-sufficient, asking for help from the community, and having leisure time, mothers can improve their own well-being. Still, they have to deal with issues like outbursts and complex child behavior, adjusting to new situations, and prejudice in society. Their ability to provide adequate care is seriously threatened by a lack of financial resources. All things considered, the research improved understanding of the experiences of Filipino mothers and suggested customized initiatives to address their unique needs. It is proposed to create a product workbook with activities meant to improve mothers' emotional and physical health. The results seek to improve the quality of life for mothers and their children with ASD by providing them with understanding and support.

Workbook Creation

As the primary objective of the conduct of the study, the process of creating the product workbook is anchored in the responses of the research participants and is driven by the principle towards well-being, which is Martin Seligman's PERMA model, first encountered in Wade et al. (2019).

The product workbook is geared towards the engagement and accomplishments facet of PERMA, with relatively simple tasks such as crossword puzzles, origami making, instructions in creating sensory toys, and even photo journaling to encourage such practice of the participants in Baird-Bate's (2019) study. Drawing out meaning from experiences; another PERMA component, can be achieved through reflective pages of the workbook, such as in goal setting and message giving.

Some portions of the workbook are informative, for one shows the many forms of respite in a "mom me time" page, and another page shows people on the ASD spectrum who achieved great things, to remind some mothers not to give up on their child as they have identified it to be among their maternal weaknesses. There is also a page that serves as a reminder that even doing or engaging in the mundanity of daily chores can serve as self-help, once again putting highlight on engagement and accomplishment in the PERMA model.

Out of the five components of well-being in the PERMA model, three (engagement, meaning, accomplishment) can be achieved by going through the contents of the workbook, as the two other PERMA components are indirect benefits. Expectedly, the contents will elicit positive emotions and stronger relationships, especially with the parent and the ASD child. The content was also condensed into fewer pages to prevent fatigue intimidation and to be time-friendly and free from pressure, given that among the weaknesses of mothers is juggling priorities. To wrap up the content, a page to extend gratitude, reflect, and remind in personalized messages from the researchers was inserted.

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